

Adsorption characteristics of lead(II) ions onto benzimidazolium based polymeric ionic liquid from aqueous solutions

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Abstract : Adsorption of metals on polymeric ionic liquid (PIL) has been increasingly used for the removal and recovery of heavy metal ions from aqueous solution. In this study, polymeric ionic liquid has been synthesized and characterized. The effect of various parameters such as pH, initial concentration of metals, concentration of polymer and time of adsorption were studied. The characteristics varied considerably with a change in the parameters. Maximum adsorption of Pb^{II} ion was found to be 80% on room temperature at pH 5.0 in 1.5 h of time. The amount of Pb^{II} absorbed or desorbed was determined using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS).

Keywords : Polymeric ionic liquid, lead, adsorption.

Introduction

As we know that heavy transition metal ions is highly toxic to human being even in very minute quantity so there will be a need to remove such toxic transition metals from water. These transition metal ions are soluble in water in the form of complexes or as ions. Since they are toxic so they could be ingested to our body if the water is not treated¹. In recent years so many technique has been utilised for the sequestration of ions from like adsorption², sedimentation³, reverse osmosis⁴, precipitation⁵.

Ionic liquids (ILs) are generally considered as environmental benign solvents and catalyst mainly due to their high thermal stability, very low flammability and negligible vapor pressure⁶. ILs showing variety of application because it is miscible with carbohydrate and polysaccharide⁷. Now a days researcher are using chitosan based biosorbant, cellulose based ionic liquid blend polymeric material for removal of metals⁸. From last few years there are so many reports available for adsorption using benzimidazolium based ionic liquids^{9,10}.

In this study, we have synthesized poly 1-allyl-3-(2-oxo-2-(2-(prop-1-en-2-yloxy)ethoxy)ethyl)-benzimidazolium (PAMBimBF₄) and applied for adsorption study of Pb^{II} metal ion. Various parameters were studied in this work including effect of pH, optimization of time,

effect of sorbent dose, effect of initial metal ion concentration, polymer concentration.

Results and discussion

Effect of pH :

For the optimization of pH, polymer concentration (1000 ppm), metal ion concentration (100 ppm) and time of adsorption 2 h with variable in pH from 2–7 for Pb^{II} was studied. It was found that maximum adsorption of Pb^{II} ion concentration 96.3 ppm was observed at pH 5. It indicates that, the pH 5 is suitable for maximum adsorption of Pb^{II}. We kept constant for optimizing parameters (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Metal adsorbed vs pH.

Effect of time :

After optimization of pH 5, we have conducted the adsorption experiment for the contact time of Pb^{II} . The duration 0.5–2.5 h was tested for the same metal ion concentration and optimized pH and we observed that maximum adsorption of Pb^{II} ion about 80 ppm in 1.5 h (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Metal adsorbed vs time.

Effect of polymer concentration :

Our next aim to examine the effect of polymer concentration on the adsorption of Pb^{II} . We vary the concentration of polymer from (100–1000) ppm at optimised pH and duration. From the result it shown that, maximum Pb^{II} 80 ppm adsorbed at 700 ppm of polymer (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Metal adsorbed vs concentration of polymer.

Adsorption of metal ion concentration :

Finally, we have carried out the amount of metal ion adsorption on constant adsorbent polymeric material under all above optimized conditions. The concentration of metal ion vary from 20–200 ppm and constant concentration of polymer 700 ppm was taken for the this adsorption studies. Eventually, we have observed that maximum adsorption of Pb^{II} was found to be 80 ppm in 1.5 h at pH 5 (Fig. 4).

From all the results, it was concluded that 80% re-

Fig. 4. Metal adsorbed vs initial metal concentration.

moval of Pb^{II} from the aqueous solution at pH 5 for 1.5 h duration. This may be due to the electronegative oxygen atom which may be capable to trap Pb^{II} in the cage of Poly-AMBimBF₄ molecule like crown ether host and guest combination.

Experimental*Materials and reagent :*

All solvents and chemicals were commercially available and used without further purification. Benzimidazole, NaBF₄, 2-hydroxy ethyl methacrylate and AIBN purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Chloroacetyl chloride and quinol from Loba. THF, Et₃N and NaH (60%) obtained from SDFCL.

Synthesis of PAMBimBF₄ :

Synthesis of poly 1-allyl-3-oxo-2-(2-(prop-1-en-2-yloxy)ethyl)-benzimidazolium (PAMBimBF₄) : 2-(prop-1-en-2-yloxy)ethyl-2-chloroacetate and 1-allyl-3-(2-oxo-2-(2-(prop-1-en-2-yloxy)ethoxy)ethyl)-benzimidazolium chloride was synthesised as per literature¹¹ (Scheme 1). Chloride based monomer ionic liquid converted to water insoluble monomer by treating with equivalent amount of NaBF₄. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 1.85 (3H, s), 4.34 (2H, d), 4.46 (2H, d), 5.25 (2H, d), 5.42 (2H, dd), 5.69 (2H, s), 5.70 (1H, s), 5.99 (1H, s), 6.17 (1H, m), 7.73 (2H, m), 8.06 (2H, m), 9.71 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 17.84, 47.40, 48.88, 62.17, 63.70, 113.86, 113.89, 120.45, 126.21, 126.75, 126.87, 130.51, 130.83, 131.49, 135.41, 143.34, 166.31, 166.41.

Polymerization of the ionic liquid monomer was carried out using AIBN as an initiator in CH₃CN solvent at 70 °C for 24 h under nitrogen atmosphere. After completion of polymerization, the solution was concentrated and poured in excess of acetone, polymer was settled down. Finally, poly 1-allyl-3-(2-oxo-2-(2-(prop-1-en-2-yloxy)-

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Scheme 1. Synthesis of PAMBimBF₄.

ethoxy)ethyl)-benzimidazolium tetrafluoro borate (PAMBimBF₄) was washed with the cold acetone and dried in vacuum.

Sorption of lead by poly-AMBimBF₄ liquid sorbent :

Optimisation of pH :

The effect of pH was studied for the adsorption of Pb^{II} ion using batch equilibrium technique. In this study, 1000 mg of adsorbent was added in a 100 ml measuring flask and 10.0 ml of 100 ppm Pb^{II} ion solution was added followed by 9.0 ml of acetate buffer solution with pH values ranging from 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0 and 7.0. The reaction mixture was kept in automatic orbital shaker for the period of 2 h at room temperature. Finally, reaction mixture was filtered over Whatmann filter paper and concentration of Pb^{II} ion in filtrate was determined by using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS).

Optimization of time :

For the optimization of time, we checked the contact time from (0.5–2.5 h) with the difference of half hour on the determined mmol g⁻¹ sorption capacity value of Pb^{II}. For this 1000 mg of sorbent was taken in 100 ml measuring flask at pH 5 and 10.0 ml of 100 ppm Pb^{II} ion solution was added. An experimental mixture was kept on orbital shaker in a selected time and concentration of unextracted Pb^{II} ion was determined by using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy.

Effect of sorbent dose :

For optimization of sorbent dose, five different mass values of sorbent in the range of 100–1000 mg used for the adsorption. A solution of 100 mg L⁻¹ of Pb^{II} ion was

prepared, buffered to pH 5 and added to the selected sorbent. This complete solution kept over automatic orbital shaker for the period of 2 h, and filtered. The conc. of Pb^{II} ion in filtrate determined by using AAS.

Effect of metal ion concentration :

Different concentration (20–200 ppm) Pb^{II} ions stock solutions were prepared at pH 5.0. From the stock solution, 100 ml solution were mixed with the 1000 mg of Poly-AMBimBF₄. The experimental mixture was then shaken by the automatic shaker for 2 h, filtered, and concentration of unextracted Pb^{II} ion was determined using AAS.

Conclusion

In this work, we synthesised the AMBimBF₄ polymer and characterized by NMR spectroscopy. The adsorption of Pb^{II} ion onto benzimidazolium based polymeric ionic liquid in aqueous solutions was studied. It may be advantageous that Poly-AMBimBF₄ acts as a applicable sorbent for the sorption of Pb^{II} ion in aqueous medium because of its high adsorption capacity due to ionic nature of polymer. It was concluded that maximum adsorption of Pb^{II} ion was found to be 80% on room temperature at pH 5.0 in 1.5 h of time.

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